

Data format: particle/pore size distribution

March 26, 2025

The aim of the following data and metadata format description is to have a standardized scheme for storing particle and pore size distributions within the CRC 1411.

During our discussions, we agreed on the following conventions:

- A comment line starts with a #.
- Decimal separator is a dot.
- Values are separated by spaces.
- Percentages are represented by decimals.
- For now: x -values are not logarithmic.
- Scientific notation for all decimal numbers, e.g. 5.364e-6. The number of digits after the decimal point should be constant within a file for readability reasons.
- We store the data in ASCII code (human-readable).
- Each file stored in the following format has the ending .psd (for particle/pore size distribution).

Description of the format

In the following, the descriptions in curly brackets need to be replaced by respective content.

For pore size distributions, the measured part of the particle and the distribution type (line 6 and 7 in Figure 1), and can hence be skipped. The distribution is discrete, and hence the x - and y -data are discrete points, and do not represent a histogram.

Figure 1: Format structure

```
1 # name of sample: {text}
2 # date of measurement: {yyyy/mm/dd hh:mm:ss (24 hours)}
3 # analysis method: {text}
4 # assumption on particle/pore geometry: {text}
5 # measured length: {text}
6 # measured part of particle: {text}
7 # type of distribution: {text}
8 # number of bins (x-data): {number}
9 # unit of x-data: {unit}
10 # bin/pore size          particle/pore count
11 {x-data}                {y-data}
12 ...
```

line 1 Name or identifier of measured sample

line 2 When was the following data collected?

line 3 Analysis method: gas adsorption, local thickness, analytical (ultra-)centrifugation (AUC, AC), laser diffraction, dynamic light scattering (DLS), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA)

line 4 Particle/pore geometry: sphere, cylinder, ellipsoid

line 5 Measured length: diameter, shortest length, equivalent spherical diameter

line 6 Which part of the particle was measured? Core, shell, core and shell?

line 7 Type of distribution,

- $Q_i, i \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 6\}$: cumulative function with intervals' endpoints as x -data,
- $q_i, i \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 6\}$: density function with intervals' midpoints as x -data,

with the most common moments

- Q_0/q_0 : number count
- Q_1/q_1 : length
- Q_2/q_2 : area
- Q_3/q_3 : volume
- Q_6/q_6 : intensity.

line 8 Number of x - and y -data pairs for consistency check

line 9 Unit of x -data values; e.g. nm, μm

line 10 Labels for x - and y -data

line 11 - end The actual x - and y - data: one pair of x - and y -value per line; separated by spaces.